

Speculation on the Relationship Between Shannon, Tsallis and Renyi Entropies

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be obtained by maximizing an entropy expression subject to the constraint $\sum_i f(e_i)$. This approach involves viewing the problem of interacting particles as a distribution of a total energy over N particles such that any distribution carries the same weight. (This is actually the microcanonical condition, with the MB case only restricting the average energy). This approach tries to minimize information required to solve the problem and is valid only if such minimal information describes the problem physically, in particular the specific interactions. In other words, one may obtain the MB distribution by considering elastic scattering $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ but these conditions are linked also to many assumptions.

In particular, the probability to collide is $f(e_i)$, i.e. the presence of a particle with energy e_i . The speed of the particle is not taken into consideration. If one considers a small box with many very slow particles and one very fast particle, it is not simply the presence of a single fast particle which determines how many collisions occur in a time Δt , but also the speed because the particle may traverse the length of the box several times in Δt creating the impression of a much higher probability. As a result, even though the MB distribution is extremely accurate in many cases experimentally, one might seek a distribution which gives more weight to high e_i values than the MB one, for certain scenarios. If one wishes to retain the physical picture of independent collisions (i.e. short range interactions), one may suggest $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $G(f(e_1))G(f(e_2))=G(f(e_3))G(f(e_4))$. The MB approach plays down high e_i because it uses $G(f)=f$ which leads to a dropping exponential $\exp(-e_i/T)$. A slower drop would be delivered by e_i to a negative exponent. We will try to show that this idea leads to the Tsallis distribution. Thus, the Tsallis approach gives more weight to high e_i values, but still considers independent elastic collisions which imply short range interactions.

One may note that the MB distribution leads to a Gaussian in velocity which is a peaked curve. In other words, for practical purposes, it seems that e_i levels close to the average e are the important ones. If one extends this idea to the Tsallis entropy, then the expression $\sum_i f(e_i)^q$ may still be somewhat close to 1. In other words, not too many e_i states have high probability, so the few dominant $f(e_i)$ have rather high probabilities which are not too greatly reduced by the power q . If this is the case, then $1+\sum_i f(e_i)^q$ is a small number compared to 1. This number may be called db such that $\ln(1+db) = db = \ln(\sum_i f(e_i)^q)$. In order to yield the MB (Shannon's entropy) result for $q=1$, one requires $1-q$ in the denominator and obtains Renyi entropy. In the case of $\sum_i f(e_i)^q$ being much less than 1, one cannot obtain the two particle scattering picture, suggesting that long range interactions may be important in the system.

The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) (Shannon's entropy) Case

The MB distribution may be obtained by considering a distribution of a total energy E among N particles such that each distribution carries the same probability weight. One may then calculate \ln of the number of states using Stirling's equation. The \ln is applied to convert a product into a

single particle sum. One may then maximize this subject to a looser constraint, namely $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$, leading to the MB distribution:

$$f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((1a)) \text{ with } \ln(\text{number of states}) = \ln(N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!) \quad ((1b))$$

where Stirling's approximation is: $\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n)$ ((1c))

The same result ((1a)) may be obtained through elastic two body scattering considerations which attempt to describe the actual physical mechanism which creates equilibrium. In other words, the equal energy distribution approach is only relevant if it is consistent with a physical scattering approach. Elastic scattering leads to:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((2a)) \text{ and } f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((2b)) \text{ so there is time reversal balance.}$$

Taking \ln of ((2b)) and equating to ((2a)) multiplied by a constant yields ((1a)). One may note, however, that the probability to react in ((2b)) is $f(e_i)$ which only accounts for the number of particles with an energy e_i and not their speed.

Even though the MB distribution is extremely accurate experimentally in numerous cases, one may consider the effect of speed in a particular example. If one imagines a small box with a number of very slowly moving particles and one very fast one, the number of collisions of the fast particle in Δt may very well depend on more than the fact that one is present. In particular, in Δt the fast particle may traverse the length of the box several times giving the sense of several fast particles being present and not one. This seems to suggest that the $\exp(-e_i/T)$ tail of the MB distribution may underestimate the probability $f(e_i)$ for high e_i in some instances. The question then seems to be: Can one remedy this while still keeping a two particle independent elastic scattering picture? We argue yes. Following the approach for the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, we consider:

$$G(f(e_1)) G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3)) G(f(e_4)) \quad ((3)) \text{ instead of } ((2b)) \text{ with } ((2a)) \text{ still in place.}$$

$$\text{Then: } \ln G(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((4))$$

We consider $d \ln(G(f))$. For the MB (Shannon's entropy case): $d \ln f = df/f$ ((5))

One may consider a slower drop-off:

$$d \ln(G(f)) = df f^{\text{power} - q} \quad ((6)) \text{ because } f < 1 \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{Integrating } ((6)) \text{ from } 1 \text{ to } f \text{ gives the Tsallis } \ln_q(f) = \{1 - f^{\text{power} - q}\} / (1 - q) \quad ((7))$$

f then should be the inverse function of $\ln_q(f)$ so:

$$f(e_i/T) = 1 - (q-1)a (e_i - u)/T^{\text{power} - 1/(1-q)}, \text{ where } a \text{ and } u \text{ are constant } ((8)) \quad (1)$$

In other words, one has a power law drop-off which is slower than a negative exponential. Thus, ((8)) could be used to describe systems in which there are short-range two body elastic collisions, but with an enhanced high e_i probability.

Renyi Entropy

The MB distribution $C \exp(-e_i/T)$ strongly suppresses high e_i probabilities leading to high $f(e_i)$ values for some e_i near e average, with T being linked to the standard deviation. Given:

$$\sum_i f(e_i) = 1 \quad ((9))$$

if $f(e_i)$ is appreciable for not too many e_i , then each $f(e_i)$ cannot become a very small number, even though they are less than 1. In such a case, $\sum_i f(e_i)^q$ may be a number a little less than 1. If this is the case:

$$db = -1 + \sum_i f(e_i)^q \quad ((10)) \text{ or}$$

$$\ln(1 + db) \approx \sum_i f(e_i)^q \quad ((11))$$

In other words, one may generalize the Tsallis entropy piece $1 - \sum_i f(e_i)^q$ to:

$$\ln(\sum_i f(e_i)^q) / (1-q) \quad ((12))$$

The $(1-q)$ is already part of the Tsallis expression and is needed, with l'Hopital's rule, to obtain Shannon's entropy for $q=1$. Now ((12)) holds even if $\sum_i f(e_i)^q \ll 1$. In such a case, one cannot expand the \ln . This seems to suggest one no longer has two body elastic scattering, i.e. short range interactions are no longer the scenario. We argue that Renyi entropy describes a system which cannot be analysed in terms of independent two body collisions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may use two body elastic scattering to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $C \exp(-e_i/T)$. This approach, however, is equivalent to distributing a total energy E among N particles with each distribution carrying equal weight. Actually, the E total restriction is relaxed to $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E_{total}$. Even though the MB result is highly accurate experimentally in many cases, it ignores the effect of speed of high e_i values and may underestimate $f(e_i)$ for high e_i in certain situations. In particular, a fast moving particle may move back and forth in a box several times in a Δt giving the sense of it representing more than one fast particle.

We suggest that one way to enhance the probability of fast particles is to consider instead of $\ln(f) = df/f$, $d \ln(G(f)) = df f^{-q}$ which drops more slowly. Integrating gives: $\ln(G(f)) = 1 - f^{-q} = \ln(f)$. The inverse of this function $\ln q$ is ((8)) which is a dropping power law, i.e. one which drops more slowly than a negative exponential. Thus, high $e_i f(e_i)$ values are enhanced. This scenario, however, still assumes independent two body elastic scattering. The MB

distribution yields high $f(e_i)$ to e_i within a standard deviation linked to T (temperature). If one expects the same result to hold (with a somewhat larger spread) for the Tsallis f power q scenario, then $\{\sum_i f(e_i)^q\}^{-1} = db$ and $\ln(1+db) = \ln(\sum_i f(e_i)^q)$. Dividing by $1-q$, as in the Tsallis case so that $q=1$ represents Shannon's entropy, one obtains Renyi entropy. If $\sum_i f(e_i)$ is not close to 1, one cannot expand \ln and one does not obtain two particle elastic scattering which seems to be linked with short range interactions. This seems to suggest long range interactions in the Renyi case.

References

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